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1. Abbreviations

BSFC: Brake Specific Fuel Consumption

CL: Closed-loop control

CMR: Compact Membrane Reactor

CO: Confidential

DI: Direct Injection

EGR: Exhaust Gas Recirculation

H2ICE: Hydrogen single-cylinder Internal Combustion Engine

HEDE: Highly Efficient Diesel Engine

ICE: Internal Combustion Engine

PFI: Port Fuel Injection

PP: Program Participants

PU: Public

RE: Restricted

RPEMS: Rapid Prototype Engine Management System

SCE: Single Cylinder Engine

VVT: Variable Valve Timing

2. Summary

This report gives an overview of the research H₂ engine, which will be tested on the testbed at the Universitat Politècnica de València in Spain. The engine is based on a single-cylinder HD-gas engine, with H₂-specific modifications and adaptations. The following chapters give an overview of the engine specifications, main features, and the sensors and actuators installed, with a special focus on the fuel injection system. In addition, an overview of the engine management system – which controls the injection system and other actuators on the engine – and the test bench integration of the H₂ICE will be provided.

3. General characteristics of the H₂ research engine

3.1 Introduction to AVL 530 series

The engine is a derivative of a series production 13 l gas engine used in trucks for on-road freight transport. This engine class (diesel or natural gas) is the most spread heavy-duty engine for long-haul trucks in Europe (major truck OEMs in Europe do have 13 l engines in their portfolio), with the overall best TCO and good performance, with a rated power of about 325-350 kW.

The AVL “HEDE” (Highly Efficient Diesel Engine) Single-Cylinder Research Base Engine was developed for fuels and lube testing and combustion research and development with a design maximum peak firing pressure of up to 300 bar. The AVL 530 crankcase has a stroke range of 120 to 170 mm and a bore range of 110 to 145 mm, covering typical engine sizes for heavy-duty truck applications.

3.2 Engine overview

The H₂ICE has a 1st and 2nd order mass balancing system and a large flywheel to minimise engine vibrations. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the front and rear views of the engine rendering, where some engine parts and subsystems can be identified, including the block, the cylinder head, the Variable Valve Timing (VVT) system, the crankcase, the flywheel cover, etc.

3.2.1 Front View

Figure 1. Front view of the H2ICE rendering.

3.2.2 Rear view

Figure 2. Rear view of the H2ICE rendering.

4. Technical specifications of the H2 research engine

The 4-stroke single-cylinder H₂ engine (H₂ICE) has been designed, according to the experimental work to be performed in the project, for research and development studies to assess the effect of different injection and combustion parameters on engine performance and emissions.

The H₂ICE engine allows flexible operation to facilitate a wide range of operation strategies targeting zero-emission operating with H₂ as fuel. The engine consists of the reinforced Basic Unit AVL Type 530 “HEDE” with a separate cylinder block. The engine is prepared for H₂ operation using different injection systems equipment for Direct Injection (DI) and Port Fuel Injection (PFI) in the intake manifold. The engine design concept does not include either oil or coolant pumps; thus, these elements must be installed in specific conditioning circuits of the test cell.

4.1 Main characteristics of the H₂ICE

The main characteristics of the H₂ICE are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the H₂ICE

Number of cylinders	1	
Cylinder bore	135 mm	
Stroke	150 mm	
Swept volume	2,15 L	
Combustion system	4-valve, 4-stroke engine	
Cylinder head	Single cylinder head / DOHC	
Fuel	Hydrogen	
Fuel system	Direct injection, Port fuel injection	
Engine management system	AVL RPEMS	
Idle speed	500 rpm	
Maximum speed	2000 rpm "high idle" 2320 rpm	(AVL base engine 3000 rpm)
Piston	Tumble and swirl piston	
Compression ratio (CR)	13:1 and 12:1	
Injector type	Liebherr H ₂ DI & PFI	
Valves per cylinder	2 intake / 2 exhaust	
Liner type	Wet, top hung	
Engine rotation	Clockwise (see front view in Figure 1)	
Timing drive type	Gear drive / belt drive to camshafts	
Timing rotation	Clockwise (see front view in Figure 1)	

Mass balancer	1 st & 2 nd order	
Engine weight (approximately)	~ 1000kg	(Without oil and coolant)
Engine inertia	8,471 kgm ²	(Including flywheel)
Oil pressure	Min. 4 bar high PFP load	

4.2 Description of the H2ICE systems

This section provides a description of the main engine systems; however, detailed sketches and pictures of all of them cannot be shown because of confidentiality.

Crankcase:

The special AVL crankcase is of vertical tunnel type, a one-piece, high-strength casting of nodular iron. Heavily reinforced, it can withstand the stresses of high-grade supercharging up to a peak cylinder pressure of up to 300 bar. The nominal main bearing diameter, with bearing shells, is 135 mm. A large side opening permits access to the crankshaft and conrod for disassembly. The compartment of the balancer shafts is located below the crankshaft oil sump and can be separated by a removable plug.

Mass balancers:

Four balancer shafts completely compensate 1st and 2nd order mass forces: two for 1st order and two for 2nd order. The crankshaft and the mass balancer shaft (compensation weights and assembled bolts) are fully balanced according to installed components as per delivery.

Camshafts:

DOHC valve control allows setting a manually variable valve timing for the two inlet and two outlet valves. Three different camshafts are available for testing: a standard camshaft and two Miller camshafts, one short and the other long. The short Miller has a 4 mm less valve lift than the standard camshaft. The long Miller has the same valve lift as the standard camshaft but closes 28° later.

Combustion chamber:

The engine has double intake ports in the cylinder head. Currently, the engine has a tumble cylinder head (with CR = 13:1) and a piston with a tumble bowl. The sparking plug and DI injector are arranged close to the middle line of the combustion chamber with a light declination. They are in a line in the cross-section of the engine.

Lubrication system:

This engine has a wet sump lube oil circuit; however, as commented, it has no oil pump. The external lubrication system and its conditioning system will be installed in the test cell at the UPV. All connections of the oil supply system are accessible from outside the engine.

The following elements must be connected to the lube oil circuit:

- Main bearings (front and rear sides)
- Piston cooling jet
- Gear train lube jet
- Mass balancer lube jet
- Cylinder head – rocker and camshaft lubrication
- Camshaft front and rear bearing

Cooling system:

Similarly to the oil circuit, the engine has no water pump, so the external coolant system and its conditioning system will be installed in the test cell at the UPV installations. This auxiliary unit will have

a water pump ($\dot{m} = 10 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $p = 0,6 \text{ bar}$), a heat exchanger ($Q = 70 \text{ kW}$) and an expansion vessel. A thermostatic water outlet temperature control is highly recommended for a smooth operation.

Boost Pressure:

External charger provides high flexibility for setting the operation conditions of the H2ICE because air management processes are much less affected by the in-cylinder conditions than a turbocharged engine. This independence from the turbocharger hardware (concerning λ , EGR rate, etc.) makes it possible to investigate different combustion parameters and their sensitivity without the influence of air management thermodynamics.

Intake Manifold:

The intake manifold has an entirely new construction because two PFI injectors are mounted directly in the intake manifold. The middle of the injectors is in line with the middle of the intake ports. Two injectors in parallel were chosen because the engine includes two inlet ports to improve the mixture of the injected hydrogen and the air. For this reason, the hydrogen flow of each port injector was halved because one injector with its normal flow rate would have been sufficient for operating the SCE.

Rails and Pipes:

A separate rail was designed for each injection technology (DI and PFI) to avoid additional mounting effort and extra-long pipes.

Injectors:

Two different H_2 injectors from the company Liebherr will be tested. The test program will start with the PFI system; one of the injectors is shown in Figure 3. It has an operating pressure of 15 bar and a fuel flow rate of 12 g/s. As already mentioned, the position of the two injectors will be directly connected to the intake manifold.

Figure 3. PFI injector.

The low-pressure direct injector (axial top feed) has an operating pressure of 30 bar and a maximum fuel flow rate of 11 g/s. It will be mounted with a light declination, positioning the blow cap close to the middle of the combustion chamber.

Figure 4. DI injector.

A wide range of blow caps, symmetrical and asymmetrical, with different angles and hole numbers, are available for testing.

4.3 Engine control system

The engine control will be implemented with a so-called “AVL RPEMS” (Rapid Prototype Engine Management System), an Electronic Control Unit with full calibration access via CAN, closed-loop control of the fuel mass to facilitate the operation at a constant lambda, and an ignition timing control to avoid knocking occurrence (based on the in-cylinder pressure monitored by the test cell instrumentation). AVL does the hardware and the programming of the functions.

The approach for the engine control consists of three independent closed-loop (CL) controllers, which have the following properties:

- Quantity-based control approach.
- Slow boost pressure (P_IM) controller (implemented in the testbed) does not impact the knock risk as lambda control (ECU task) is very fast.
- Smooth variations as Lambda and Torque are constant. Safe load increase, as lambda control is faster than boost pressure control from the test cell.
- Safe operation with EGR thanks to its slow variation, fast knock monitoring, and Lambda control.

Figure 5. Sketch of the H2ICE control system.

The following block diagram shows the RPEMS communication architecture:

Figure 6. RPEMS communication architecture.

The following system overview shows the main RPEMS inputs (from sensors) and outputs (components the RPEMS takes control of through control actions):

Figure 7. Inputs of the RPEMS and components controlled.

5. Sensorization of the H2 research engine

This section is devoted to describing the instrumentation that the engine is provided with. Additional sensors will be installed later when the H2ICE is commissioned at the test cell.

5.1 Sensors and their positions on the H2 research engine

The following table includes the list of the sensors on the engine:

Table 2. Engine instrumentation.

Low-pressure intake/exhaust transducers	2 x AVL - GS11D-S0
In-cylinder high-pressure transducer	AVL - GH15DK
Rail pressure sensors	2 x General Electric - PTX5072-TA-A3-CA-H0-PA
Rail temperature sensors	2 x Bosch - NTCM8-HS
Camshaft sensors	2 x Bosch - PG3.5
Crankshaft sensor	Bosch - DG6
Temperature sensor on oil module	PT100
Temperature sensor in the coolant circuit	PT100

The following paragraphs briefly describe these sensors.

AVL – GS11D-S0:

They are low-pressure transducers. One will be installed in the intake manifold and the other in the exhaust manifold to measure the instantaneous pressures of the gas exchange. These sensors have been provided with the engine and will be mounted during the engine set-up on the test bed.

AVL – GH15DK:

It is a high-pressure piezoelectric transducer with a high endurance against knocking than the regular pressure sensors in the manifolds. Even though it is not visible due to its location inside the duct drilled into the cylinder head for accessing the combustion chamber, the following picture shows a detail of its location.

Figure 8. Detail of the GH15 DK sensor location at the cylinder head.

Rail pressure sensors:

They are located at one extreme of the two hydrogen rails feeding the DI and the PFI injectors. Its signal is a crucial input for the RPEMS to control the amount of H₂ injected, as shown in Figure 79.

Figure 9. Detail of the rail pressure sensor installed at the PFI rail.

Rail temperature sensors:

They are located at one extreme (on the opposite side of the pressure sensors) of the two hydrogen rails feeding the DI and the PFI injectors.

Figure 10. Detail of the rail temperature sensor installed at the PFI rail.

Camshaft sensors:

These two sensors (one for the intake valves camshaft and one for the exhaust valves camshaft) allow determining the rotation position of the camshafts, a key issue to control the VVT operation. Its signal is also an essential input for the RPEMS to control H₂ injection and ignition phasing, as shown in Figure 711.

Figure 11. Detail of the camshaft sensor installed on the cylinder head.

Crankshaft sensor:

This sensor allows determining the rotation position of the crankshafts. Its signal is a key input for the RPEMS to control the H₂ injection and the ignition phasings, as shown in Figure 712.

Figure 12. Crankshaft sensor.

Coolant temperature sensor:

It is a thermoresistance PT100 sensor, with a higher accuracy than conventional thermocouples, that allows determining the engine coolant temperature, an important parameter to guarantee the proper operation of the engine and its safety. The signal is an input for the RPEMS, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 13. Detail of the coolant temperature sensor installed at the inlet pipe.

Oil temperature in the oil distributor block:

Like the coolant temperature sensor, it is a thermoresistance PT100 that allows determining the engine oil temperature, an important parameter to guarantee the proper operation of the engine and its safety. The following figure shows a detail of the oil distributor block with the sensor.

Figure 14. Detail of the oil temperature sensor installed at the oil distributor.

Several additional sensors will be installed during the testbed set-up, as described in the next section.

6. Test bench integration

This section describes the test bench requirements for the H2ICE experimental campaign. According to the project schedule, Task 6.2 (H2ICE system supply and commissioning at the test bench) has not officially started when preparing this report. However, the test bench and engine commissioning at the UPV installations are in progress and advanced with respect to the work planning. A brief description of the works already performed, and the feasible testing activities (once the commissioning has been completed) are also summarized.

6.1 Test bench requirements

According to the deliverable D3.2 (Critical Parameter Identification), several time-averaged and instantaneous signals are required for the experimental work. The main instantaneous signals have already been described in the previous section (instantaneous in-cylinder and manifold pressures), as their sensors are provided with the H2ICE. Still, some others will be installed (in fact, some are currently being installed) during the test cell and engine setup. In summary, they are described below.

Additional instantaneous signals

A current clamp for the injector and a current clamp for the ignition coil will be used to measure their corresponding signals, essential information to characterise the operating point of the H2ICE. An acquisition and processing unit (Indication system) will allow the registration of all the instantaneous signals. The two signals provided by an angular encoder (the first one with a pulse each crankshaft revolution and the second used as an external clock) allow sampling of all the signals for the instantaneous acquisition so that they all are measured synchronised with the crankshaft angle.

Time-averaged signals

A fully instrumented test cell is required, so it will include a dynamometer, engine instrumentation to measure main operation parameters (speed, torque, fluids mass flow, pressure, and temperature at different locations of the gas and liquid circuits -coolant and oil -) and finally emissions. The complete list of variables described in Deliverable D3.2 has been specifically adapted for the single-cylinder engine installation, with some slight changes agreed with AVL, as indicated in the “Comment” columns of Table 3 and Table 4¹.

Table 3. Mean variables to be measured at the H2ICE test bench. Fluids pressures and temperatures.

Signal name	Description	Comment
Temperatures and pressures Intake side		
T_IA	IntakeAir:TempUpstreamAirFilter	Not applicable
P_IA	IntakeAir:PresUpstreamAirFilter	Not applicable
T_11	IntakeAir:TempDownstrAirFilter#1	OK
P_11	IntakeAir:PresDownstrAirFilter#1	OK
T_21	IntakeAir:TempCompressorOutB#1	Not applicable
P_21	IntakeAir:BoostPressureB#1	Not applicable
T_2_1	IntakeAir:TempDownstreamIC#1	Not applicable
P_2_1	IntakeAir:PresDownstreamIC#1	Not applicable
T_IM	IntakeAir:TempIntakeManifold	OK
P_IM	IntakeAir:PresIntakeManifold	OK
P_MAN	Low pressure indication intake port	OK
Temperatures and pressures Outtake side		
P_EXH	Low pressure indication exhaust port	OK
T_31	EngExh:TempExhManifoldBank#1	OK
P_31	EngExh:PresExhManifoldBank#1	OK
T_41	EngExh:TempUpstrAftertrBank#1	Not applicable
P_41	EngExh:PresUpstreamAftertrBank#1	Not applicable
Ambient air condition		
P_0_A	BarometricPressure	OK
T_0	Test Cell Temperature	OK
EGR		
T_EGRHE_I	HeatExchangerEGR:GasTempln	OK
P_EGRHE_I	HeatExchangerEGR:GasPressin	OK
T_EGRHE_O	HeatExchangerEGR:GasTempOut	OK
P_EGRHE_O	HeatExchangerEGR:GasPressOut	OK
T_HEEGR_I	HeatExchangerEGR:TempCoolantIn	TBC
P_HEEGR_I	HeatExchangerEGR:PressCoolantIn	TBC
T_HEEGR_O	HeatExchangerEGR:TempCoolantOut	TBC
P_HEEGR_O	HeatExchangerEGR:PressCoolantOut	TBC
Coolant condition		
T_W_I	Temp:CoolantOuterCircuitEngIn	OK
P_W_I	Pres:CoolantEngIn	TBC
T_W_O	Temp:CoolantOuterCircuitEngOut	OK
P_W_O	Pres:CoolantEngOut	TBC
T_HEIC_I	Intercooler1:CoolantTempln	Not applicable
P_HEIC_I	CoolantPressIntercoolerInlet	Not applicable
T_HEIC_O	Intercooler1:CoolantTempOut	Not applicable
P_HEIC_O	CoolantPressIntercoolerOut	Not applicable
H2 condition		
T_FUEL_I	FuelCons:TempFuelSupply	OK - 2x
P_FUEL_I	FuelCons:FuelSupplyPressure	OK - 2x
T_FUEL_O	FuelCons:TempFuelReturn	Not applicable
P_RAIL	FuelRailPressure	OK
Oil condition		
T_OIL	Temp:OilMainDuctBank#1	OK
P_OIL	Pres:OilMainDuctBank#1	OK
Engine performance, exhaust emissions and miscellaneous		
P_CRANKC	Pressure:Crankcase	TBC
P_EXPANS	PressureExpansionTank-Air	TBC

TBC: Complementary variable that, even interesting, will not affect the analysis quality if unavailable. UPV will try to measure it.

¹ “Not applicable” in general, it corresponds to variables that are usually measured in a multi-cylinder engine but not a single-cylinder engine installation.

Table 4. Mean variables to be measured at the H2ICE test bench. Performance, emissions and others.

Signal name	Description	Comment	Signal name	Description	Comment
Engine performance, exhaust emissions and miscellaneous			Engine performance, exhaust emissions and miscellaneous		
BMEP	MeanEffectivePressure	OK	MF_NO_TP	TailPipe:MassFlowNO	Not applicable
BS_NOX_EO	EngOut:BrakeSpecificNOxEmission	OK	MF_NOX_EO	EngOut:MassFlowNOX	OK*
BS_NOX_EO_S	EngOut:BrakeSpecNOXEmiss(REG)	TBC	MF_NOX_TP	TailPipe:MassFlowNOx	Not applicable
BS_NOX_TP	TailPipe:BrakeSpecificNOXEmiss	Not applicable	MF_O2_EO	EngOut:MassFlowO2	OK
BS_NOX_TP_S	TailPipe:BrakeSpecNOXEmiss(REG)	Not applicable	MF_O2_TP	TailPipe:MassFlowO2	Not applicable
BS_O2_EO	EngOut:BrakeSpecificO2Emission	OK	MF_THC_EO	EngOut:MassFlowTHC	OK*
BS_O2_TP	Tailpipe:BrakeSpecificO2Emission	Not applicable	MF_THC_TP	TailPipe:MassFlowTHC	Not applicable
BSFC	BrakeSpecificFuelConsumption	OK	N	AveragedEngSpeed	OK
FD_AFST	FuelData:StoechAir/FuelRatio	OK	NO_EO	EngOut:NOVolumeConc,wet	OK*
FD_DESC	FuelTyp:Description	Not applicable	NO_FT1	FTIR:NO VolumeConc,wet	OK*
FD_ID	FuelData:UniqueFuelIdentifier	Not applicable	NO_TP	TailPipe:NOVolumeConc,wet	Not applicable
FD_NCALV	FuelData:NetCalorificValue	Not applicable	NO2_EO	EngOut:NO2 VolumeConc,wet	OK*
FD_RHO15	FuelData:DensityAt15°C	Not applicable	NO2_FT1	FTIR:NO2 VolumeConc,wet	OK*
H2O_FT1	FTIR:H2O VolumeConc,wet	OK	NO2_TP	TailPipe:NO2 VolumeConc,wet	Not applicable
I_FILE	IndiEquipment:ResultFileName	OK	NOX_EO	EngOut:NOxVolumeConc,wet	OK*
ID_CURVE	Measurement:CurveID	OK	NOX_FT1	FTIR:NOX VolumeConc,wet	OK*
ID_MEAS	Measurement:MeasurementID	OK	NOX_TP	TailPipe:NOxVolumeConc,wet	Not applicable
IMEP	IndicatedMeanEffPresCyl#All	OK	O2_EO	EngOut:O2VolumeConc,dry	OK
LAV	AirExcessRatio(MassFlowMeas)	OK	O2_FT1	FTIR:O2 VolumeConc,wet	OK*
lav	AirExcessRat(MassFlowMeas)(Onl)	OK	O2_TP	TailPipe:O2VolumeConc,dry	Not applicable
M_FUEL_STR	FuelMassPerStroke	OK	PED	ActPedalPosition	Not applicable
m_fuel_str	FuelMassPerStroke(Online)	OK	PWR	AveragedEngPowerOutput	OK
md	Engine Torque	OK	RHO_FUEL	FuelDensityAtActualTemperature	OK
MD	AveragedLeverArmTorque	OK	RHO_IA	DensityIntakeAir	OK
MF_EGR	EGR:MassFlowEGRLine	OK	RT_CBAL_EO	EngOut:CBal(MassFlowMeas-Exh)	OK
mf_exh	Online:MassFlowExhaust	OK	RT_CBAL_TP	TailPipe:CBal(MassFlowMeas-Exh)	Not applicable
MF_EXH	EngOut:MassFlowExhaustWet	OK	I_BAT	BatteryAmpere	TBC
mf_fuel	MassFlowFuel(AveragedValue)	OK	U_BAT	BatteryVoltage	OK
MF_FUEL	MassFlowFuel(AnalogOnlineValue)	OK	V_FUEL_STR	FuelVolumePerStroke(StdCond15°C)	OK
mf_ia	IntakeAir:MassFlow(Online)	OK	VEFF	VolEff:TotalWetBank#1	Not applicable
MF_IA	IntakeAir:MassFlowBank#1	OK	VEFF_IM	VolEff:IntakeManifold	OK
MF_NO_EO	EngOut:MassFlowNO	OK*	VF_BBY	VolumeFlowBlowBy	OK
			H2 in BBY	H2 measurement in Blow-by	TBC
			H2 sensor	measurement for safety requirements	OK

TBC: Complementary variable that, even interesting, will not affect the analysis quality if unavailable. UPV will try to measure it.

OK*: FTIR is available but not during the complete experimental campaign. Horiba will always be available.

NOx (including NO and NO2) and unburned hydrocarbons will be measured by a HORIBA MEXA-ONE and, during part of the experimental campaign, with an FTIR gas analyser. O₂ concentrations at the intake and exhaust lines will be measured with a M&C GENTWO gas analyser with a measurement range of 0-100%; this will be used to calculate the EGR rate in both conventional and oxy-fuel conditions, where O₂ concentration will exceed the range of traditional gas analysers because N₂ is not present in the oxidiser flow.

Special effort will be put on the thermal instrumentation to perform accurate thermal balances, a key issue to assess the H2ICE and CMR synergy.

6.2 H2-ICE/test bench adaptation

A brief description of the adaptation works already performed in the test bench at the UPV installations is provided in this section.

The simplified test bench scheme is shown in Figure 15. The original layout of the test bench has been adapted for supplying not only air but also pure O₂ from a pressurised tank. The latter will be used to operate the H2ICE engine under oxy-fuel combustion in the latest stage of the experimental campaign, while for conventional combustion, an external compressor will be used to provide the compressed air to reproduce boost conditions. In any case, the installation has been adapted to be flexible to switch between conventional and oxy-fuel combustion operations.

Figure 15. Basic sketch of the H2ICE test bench.

The H₂ and O₂ feeding flows are measured and controlled using Bronkhorst F113AC and F203AV thermal mass flow meters, respectively. A knife-gate valve downstream of the settling chamber in the exhaust line will allow controlling the exhaust back pressure, and a high-pressure EGR system provides the required levels of conditioned EGR. External oil and cooling conditioning circuits are independent of the engine.

With the test cell adaptation in progress, the engine has been mounted on the test bench, as seen in Figure 16. It is currently being connected to the auxiliary circuits, and its instrumentation is in progress, as described in the previous sections. The engine and the test bench will be ready to start the validation activities in about 4-5 weeks (3 months earlier than the project schedule) and then perform the experimental studies.

Figure 16. H2ICE engine on the test bench.

6.3 Feasible testing activities

The objective of the H2ICE experimental campaign is to characterise the engine operation targeting zero NO_x emissions (the most critical pollutant that will be produced). Minimising H₂ consumption is also important; however, as the H2ICE is previewed to finally operate with the CMR (that will use heat and electricity from the H2ICE), optimal global performance does not necessarily coincide with optimal H2ICE operation. Moreover, CMR performances and specifications recommend exploring H2ICE operation in a wide range of settings and hardware configurations to assess the trade-off between key H2ICE outputs: thermal and brake powers, NO_x and H₂ consumption.

The experimental work will focus on a limited number of stationary speed-load conditions because the H2ICE will operate at stationary conditions when installed in the complete powerplant. Considering these requirements, the installation has been designed to cover any operating condition of the original engine map of the multi-cylinder engine version shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Engine map of the multi-cylinder engine version of the H2ICE.

For each operating condition, both settings and hardware parameters such as lambda (independent from the gas exchange and MFB50%), EGR rate, injection system or VVT can be investigated independently. The choice of hardware includes DI (with a selection of different blow caps) and PFI; and two different cylinder heads (with tumble and swirl).

Starting with the tumble cylinder head and PFI injector, several selected operating points, such as:

- High speed at low and medium loads.
- Intermediate speed at medium load (typical road load point for the engine in its corresponding vehicle class) and high load.
- Maximum torque and power.
- Best BSFC conditions.
- Low speed and high load (critical conditions for knocking).
- Others

They can be tested without and with different EGR rates in a combination of different lambda levels and

injection and ignition timings for assessing the best engine performances. Afterwards, the operation with the DI injector will be evaluated to compare with the PFI injector.

The possibility of installing a swirl cylinder head unit is being considered; most promising points with PFI and DI would be explored again to assess the trends with the setting.

Starting with a small number of operating points for selecting the most promising hardware regarding best engine performance and exhaust emissions, a rough calibration of the entire engine map with the best hardware combination can be done.

The possible settings and hardware variations that can be explored are:

- Air-fuel ratio: Lean burn combustion is key in exploring low-temperature conditions to achieve zero NO_x. It will be swept in the range where combustion is stable.
- EGR operation: EGR is the second strategy to diminish gas temperature and NO_x emissions; thus, a complete experimental characterisation is previewed.
- Cylinder charge motion: Two cylinder heads are planned to be tested, one promoting swirl formation and another promoting tumble, to find which charge motion is more favourable for H₂ combustion.
- VVT operation: The trade-off with EGR and lambda to maximise efficiency and minimise NO_x will be explored.
- Compression ratio: It provides an additional degree of freedom to explore the trade-off between engine efficiency and NO_x emissions.
- Port and direct injection: Due to the low density of H₂, the port injection directly affects the air intake flow; thus, comparing these two injection configurations is scheduled.

Finally, the effect of the H₂ purity to reproduce the CMR malfunction, where H₂ can be contaminated with other chemical species, can also be evaluated by feeding the H₂ICE with a specifically prepared fuel with the required content of NH₃, CH₄, CH₄O, C₂H₆O.